

EXPRESSION OF EDUCATIONAL IDEAS IN KARAKALPAK TOLGAWS

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Annotaciya: Biz bul maqalamızda tolgawdın janrlıq ózgesheligi hám onıń qaraqalpaq xalıq awızeki dóretpeleri qatarında payda bolıwı, búgingi kúnde ádebiyatımızdaǵı tolgawlardıń áhmiyeti hám olardıń jaslar tárbiyasında tutqan ornı haqqında sóz ettik.

Gilt sózler: Folklor, tolgaw, jıraw, danalıq sózler, didaktika.

Аннотация: В данной статье мы говорили о жанровых отличиях «толгау» и его появлении в каракалпакском фольклоре, значении «толгау» в нашей литературе сегодня и их роли в воспитании молодежи.

Ключевые слова: фольклор, толгау, джирав, мудрые слова, дидактика.

Annotation: In this article, we talked about the genre differences of “tolgaw” and its appearance in Karakalpak folklore, the importance of “tolgaw”s in our literature today and their role in youth education.

Key words: Folklore, tolgaw, jiraw, wise words, didactics.

It is characteristic of all nations to raise the future generation to be suitable successors, educated, knowledgeable and wise. There are many social, historical, scientific, political, cultural factors affecting human education. Belles-lettres is also included among them. Therefore, we aimed to study the expression of educational thoughts in “tolgaw”, which is considered one of the folklore works in this article.

In accordance with President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev Order PD-No.4320, “About the measures for further development of the art of Bakhshilik” on May 14, 2019, the great importance of the ethical upbringing of young generation, studying our national art and rich folkloric heritage widely scope of education were approved [1]. Studying the “terme-tolgaws”, which are considered the heritage of “jiraw-shayirs” in the fulfillment of the tasks set, and analyzing their impact on the upbringing of the youth are considered as important problems of today’s modern folkloristics.

Each work has its own uniqueness and value. “Tolgaws” are also considered valuable works that have lived for several centuries. ““Tolgaw” is the greatest cultural heritage left by our ancestors. It is considered comforting with the joy of our people since early times” [3,p.3]. Indeed, we see great educational content in these works. At present, in schools and educational institutions, one of the tasks of every writer-pedagogue is to fully study the genre difference and content of tolgaws and explain them to youth.

Karakalpak folklore has been studied by folklorist scientists, the emergence of tolgavs, generic differences, and their performers have been mentioned in several scientific works [2].

In this article, we decided to study the samples of “tolgaw” given in the work “Korakalpoq Tolgawlari” by scientist K. Mambetov as an object. K. Mambetov, candidate of philological sciences, divided them into three groups depending on the generic difference of “tolgaw” and the periods of its appearance in Karakalpak folklore.

1. General “tolgaw”s.
2. Historical “tolgaw”s.
3. The author saved “tolgaw”s.

The first group is said to have moved from the oldest times to the present day to “tolgaw” from examples of folk wise, and these are considered to be the foundation of folk didactic teaching, exhortation poems [3,p.5]. In fact, the “tolgaws” that belong to this group consist of proverbs that have been told by the people, each line of which expresses an educational character. For example:

Jaqsınıń barsań qasına,
“Beri kel” dep shaqırar.
Jamannıń barsań qasına,
Ash jolbarıstay aqırar.
or,
Hadal kásip az emes,
Iqtıyat bol haramnan.
Jaqsılıqtı úmit qıl,

Jillı jüzli adamnan [3,p.9].

In these “tolgaws” thoughts are expressed urging people to know good and bad people, to find their place in life, and to get a good profession.

Hadal kásip az emes,

Iqtıyat bol haramnan,

-no matter what profession he chooses in his ranks, he calls to be honest, to be a perfect person who has imbibed human qualities.

Jaqsılıqtı úmit qıl,

Jillı jüzli adamnan,

- by saying that no evil will come from a loving person, therefore, while saying that we should live expecting good from people, he calls us to show beautiful and beautiful feelings to each other.

Parents are the most precious and great person for a child. Fulfilling their duty is the child's duty before them. It is mentioned in Karakalpak "tolgaws" as follows:

Aq sút bergen ananıń,

Balada haqı kóp bolar.

Atannıń qádirin bilmegen,

Balanıń bası xor bolar [3,p.9].

Father and mother overcome various difficulties to give birth to a child and join the ranks of intelligent, knowledgeable people. Throughout their lives, they wish for their child and think about taking care of it. A smart, loving child should not forget and remember these things:

Erliktiń bolar eń zorı,

Ata-anańnıń kewilin tap.

Olar ómir ğamxorı,

Ósirgen seni ardaqlap [3,p.12].

Advice words about the fact that such parents are valuable and priceless people are very well given in "tolgaws" and they are very important in the upbringing of the youth.

In the examples above, we have mentioned about the duties of the child towards the parents and the need to honor them. For example:

Atası jaman qandaydı

Qamaқтаğı maldaydı.

Enesi jaman qandaydı,

Dáryağa salğan saldaydı [3,b.16].

In the quoted short lines, there is a deep thought-provoking idea that parents should educate their children and show them the right path, otherwise their children will not be able to find their place in society and life in the future.

When a person comes into the world, he lives striving for perfection until the end of his life. He learns what path to choose in life by observing the behavior of others, thinking and thinking. Then he listens to the advice of the elders. In the following "tolgaws" it is mentioned about what a man should be in life, the qualities necessary for his nature:

Qanatın ursa qıyağa,

Qarshıға qalar ushıwdan.

Jigitke kelgen páleket,

Jónli-jónsiz ashıwdan.

or,

Jigit bolsañ shalqar bol,

Iziñe ergen shalqısın,

Sózleriñdi esitip,

Tula boyı balqısın.

Jigit bolsañ qanıq bol,

Hárbir iske qayım bol, [3,p.12]

-in the lines of everyone should know the word of speech, where to sit, anger is an enemy, intelligence is a friend, a young man's words should be as sharp as a sword, so that the people will respect and trust him. These are not empty words of wise. All of them are valuable words derived from the experiences and lessons of this life. "Tolgaw" lived in the

mouth of the people for centuries. That's why they talk about the smallest details of life and advise one by one how a person should behave in any situation:

Aqkókirek bolıp ańqılday berme,
Maqtanshaq bolıp shańqılday berme.
Kópshilikten tıs jerseń,
Orınsız jerde pańqılday berme.
Men zorman dep qańqılday berme.
Óziń sóylep, zańqılday berme.
Jigitlikke jaraspaydı,
Áytewir sózge tońqılday berme.
Jaqsı jigittiń belgisi,
Kelgen qonaǵına taq turadı.
Jaman jigittiń belgisi,
Men zorman dep lap uradı [3,p.14].

If the meaning of works of art is to recognize life through art, to deliver it to people in a beautiful form, "tolgaws" can fulfill this task more than enough. Every line, every word in it has a deep meaning, rich in intelligence. So, the creators of "tolgaw" were also sages who knew how to draw correct conclusions from life events.

In conclusion, didactic and educational thoughts are deeply embedded in the content of the work in "Tolgaw", which has become one of its genre features. Each line of "Tolgaw" is written with words of wise, calling a person to think deeply, to know life intelligently, to become a perfect person. That's why "Tolgaws" have a special role in educating young people to be loyal, audacious and brave.

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